

On-Chip Interferometric Wavefront Sensing and Correction Using a Photonic Integrated Circuit

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ABSTRACT

The development of compact, high-speed adaptive optics systems is essential for advancing fields such as ground-based astronomy or free-space optical communications. This work presents a photonic integrated circuit (PIC) proposal for real-time sensing and correction of wavefront aberrations. The device aims to perform direct, on-chip measurement of phase differences across an incoming optical wavefront and apply dynamic corrections, enabling enhanced optical system performance in rapidly changing environments.

Unlike traditional adaptive optics systems, which rely on bulky and mechanically complex components such as deformable mirrors and Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensors, our approach leverages the scalability and robustness of photonic integration. The proposed PIC architecture's working principle is based on the phenomenon of interferometry, combined with tunable photonic components such as thermo-optic phase shifters, to actively compensate for detected aberrations. The proposed technique presents the novelty of not requiring image formation for computing wavefront sensing, which can lead to potential applications in solar adaptive optics. This integration enables a fully integrated, low-power solution that is compatible with commercial foundries through multi-project wafer (MPW) runs, facilitating cost-effective implementation and easing the development/demonstration program.

This first proposal should be compatible with commercial photonic integrated foundries, such as InP, SOI or SiN, and has been validated through simulations and a mathematical model. Its operation wavelength is 1550 nm, which is an interesting band in the near-infrared for science targets in astronomy and a common wavelength in free-space optical communication.

Keywords: Integrated photonics, wavefront sensing, wavefront correction, interferometry

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1. INTRODUCTION

Photonics is a branch of physics that develops and applies advanced technologies for the generation, manipulation, and detection of light. This field has enabled a wide range of applications, from optical fibre and quantum communication systems [1], to applications such as photonic biosensors in clinical diagnosis [2] or the polarisation-gradient cooling of trapped ions [3].

Astro-photonics is an emerging branch of astronomy and applied physics that exploits photonic technologies for astronomical instrumentation. Photonic components, such as optical fibres, are now widely used in modern instruments [4]. An example is the WEAVE (WHT Enhanced Area Velocity Explorer) multi-object spectrograph (MOS) on the 4.2-m William Herschel Telescope in La Palma, which will begin surveys around April 2026, using approximately 70% of the telescope's observing time [5].

The on-chip integration of photonic components has attracted significant attention in recent years. Such integration offers the potential to miniaturise astronomical instruments as well as provide new features and capabilities. To date, one of the most successful astronomical instruments that employs integrated photonics is the beam-combiner of the GRAVITY instrument at the Very Large Telescope Interferometer (VLTI) [6, 7]. This system is based on the principle of a "pairwise static ABCD" scheme that enables interferometric combination of light between the four telescopes present at the VLTI. This instrument has revolutionised infrared astronomy by providing high-precision astronomy. GRAVITY has achieved scientific results such as the observation of faint sources as magnitude 19 in the K-band, due to its fringe tracker [8] or the determination of the first dynamical masses of a classical Be + stripped, and bloated pre-subdwarf binary [9].

In this work, an integrated photonic wavefront sensor and corrector is proposed. The main advantage of this approach over traditional wavefront sensors lies in its ability to perform wavefront sensing without imaging formation by using the phenomenon of interferometry. This feature reduces computational requirements and simplifies the adaptive optics architecture, offering potential benefits for applications in astronomy as well as optical and quantum communications.

Furthermore, this approach presents advantages in wavefront sensing of extended sources, such as the Sun. Solar wavefront sensing is especially challenging due to the low contrast compared to night time observations and the limitation produced in the spatial resolution, which affects the accuracy in the wavefront reconstruction. The photonic wavefront sensor considered here was originally introduced in [10, 11]. In this work, a modification of this circuit is performed for not only wavefront sensing but also wavefront correction on the same chip, by using phase modulators (PM) is proposed.

The paper is structured as follows: section 2 presents an overview of adaptive optics systems and the challenges that our approach aims to overcome. Section 3 presents the on-chip wavefront sensing and correction proposed. Section 4 presents the results obtained in the full system simulation. Section 5 introduce a layout implementation proposal. Section 6 presents the conclusions obtained from this work.

2. ADAPTIVE OPTICS SYSTEM

Adaptive optics is a technique that is widely used in multiple fields, such as microscopy [12] or ophthalmology [13]. In astronomy, it plays a crucial role in correcting wavefront aberrations introduced by the Earth's atmosphere. These aberrations arise from atmospheric turbulence caused by variations in temperature, pressure, and weather conditions. Their effects include image blurring, image motion (commonly observed as stellar twinkling), the formation of speckle patterns, and limitations in achievable angular resolution, among others [14, 15].

In the field of optical and quantum communications, atmospheric turbulence can be a really critical factor, as it can induce intensity fluctuations, beam wander, misalignment losses at the receiver, and beam spreading during propagation [16].

To mitigate these effects, astronomers have developed adaptive optics (AO) systems. An adaptive optics system measures the magnitude and spatial distribution of wavefront aberrations and subsequently compensates for them, thereby restoring the incoming wavefront to its original planar, collimated form. Figure 1 depicts a traditional adaptive optics system. The incoming atmospheric distorted light enters the telescope, and a beam-splitter splits the light in a certain ratio. Part of the light is used for performing the science, and the

remainder is directed to a wavefront sensor. The figure shows a traditional Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensor (SHWFS) [17, 18].

Figure 1: Traditional adaptive optics system. A beam splitter divides the incoming light in a certain ratio. Part of the light is used for performing the science in the science detector, and the remainder is used for performing the wavefront sensing. Then, a control unit is used to control the deformable mirror and correct the wavefront aberrations.

A traditional SHWFS employs an array of microlenses positioned in the pupil plane, where each microlens forms an image of the observed source. For an incoming planar wavefront, each of these images will be spatially equally spaced. When wavefront aberrations are introduced, the spots are displaced from its original locations. By computing the distance between the centroids in the original and the distorted wavefront image, a measure of the wavefront aberration can be determined.

This technique is widely used during night-time observations, and telescopes such as the W.M. Keck telescopes [19] or the Gemini South Telescope [20] employ it. However, direct application to solar observations introduces several challenges due to the need for imaging in wavefront sensing. The first challenge is the computing cost of the system, since a bunch of images have to be analysed in quasi-real time, which increases the complexity of the design. This limitation affects not only astronomical applications but also optical and quantum communication systems.

The second challenge arises from the extended nature of the Sun. While several solar telescopes employ this type of wavefront sensor, such as the Swedish 1-m Solar Telescope [21] or the 1.5-m GREGOR Solar Telescope [22, 23], the low contrast in solar images compared with night-time observations complicates wavefront measurement. Moreover, small-scale structures of the Sun, such as granulations or sunspots, are required as reference features for performing this technique. This limits the size of the microlenses present in the wavefront sensor to a minimum of 8 cm, to have enough resolution to compute displacements.

3. WAVEFRONT SENSING AND CORRECTION METHOD

To solve this limitation, this group proposed a technique for performing wavefront sensing without the need to perform imaging. The proposed adaptive optics system is shown in Figure 2. The traditional wavefront sensor is

now replaced by a photonic integrated circuit (PIC). The approach also employs an array of microlenses in the pupil plane, similar to a Shack–Hartmann wavefront sensor; however, instead of a CCD camera in the focal plane, an array of photodetectors is used to capture the light, reducing the cost of the AO system.

Figure 2: Proposal of adaptive optics system. The deformable mirror has been substituted by a regular mirror, and an array of phase modulators are used for performing the wavefront correction.

An array of optical fibres couples the light to the photonic integrated circuit. In this work, a system analogous to a classical wavefront reconstructor is presented in which the deformable mirror has been replaced by a regular mirror. Wavefront reconstruction is then performed using an array of phase modulators (PMs). These phase modulators will delay the incoming aberrated optical signal to reconstruct its original shape.

The IP-WFS schematic was previously presented in [10, 11] and is reproduced in Figure 3. In the first stage, an optional semiconductor optical amplifier (SOA) may be included to enhance the dynamic range of the system. The light then passes through a multimode interferometer (MMI) which acts as a beam splitter. Part of the light will be sent to a photodetector that will perform a measurement of the input light intensity. The remainder will be sent to a PM.

Since interferometry is a method that relies on the symmetry between both optical paths, an initial calibration stage is required. Two known signals, in phase with each other, will be inserted in both inputs. Then, the phase delay introduced by the PM will be modified until a maximum is reached. At this point, the delays in both paths are equalised, ensuring that subsequent measurements accurately reflect the phase difference between the inputs.

Finally, an MMI will perform the interferometry between the two input signals, detecting the phase difference introduced by the atmosphere. The optical intensity detected by the photodiode PD_1 is related to the phase difference by the relationship presented in Equation (1).

$$I(\mathbf{r}) = I_1(\mathbf{r}) + I_2(\mathbf{r}) + 2\sqrt{I_1(\mathbf{r})I_2(\mathbf{r})} \cos(\phi_1 - \phi_2) \quad (1)$$

where $I(\mathbf{r})$ corresponds to the intensity received by the photodetector, $I_1(\mathbf{r})$ and $I_2(\mathbf{r})$ correspond to the optical intensities of each of the inputs and $\phi_1 - \phi_2$ to the phase difference between both inputs.

Figure 3: IP-WFS schematic.

This circuit can be extended, with additional phase modulators, to perform not only wavefront sensing but also wavefront correction, as illustrated in Figure 4. An array of microlenses is placed in the pupil plane, coupling a portion of the wavefront to an optical fibre. For each pair of inputs, the signal is introduced to a beam splitter, which could be implemented with an MMI if full integration of the instrument is wanted. Then, part of this light is introduced to the IP-WFS, which will deliver a set of electrical outputs. A PM controller will use the interferometric results delivered by the IP-WFS and inject a current to the PM that will modify its refractive index. As a result, the PM will generate a phase delay for each of the inputs, correcting the phase delays introduced by the atmosphere.

Figure 4: Proposed wavefront sensing and reconstruction system.

This modification introduces some advantages, since wavefront correction is performed with no need to use deformable mirrors. This makes it a low-cost solution for adaptive optics systems. With this implementation, the corrected outputs will correspond to Equations (2)-(3):

$$I_1(\mathbf{r})_{corr.} = \frac{I_1(\mathbf{r})}{2} e^{-j\theta_1} \quad (2)$$

$$I_2(\mathbf{r})_{corr.} = \frac{I_2(\mathbf{r})}{2} e^{-j\theta_2} \quad (3)$$

where θ_1 and θ_2 correspond to the phase correction introduced by the phase modulator.

3.1 Light coupling to the instrument

A major challenge in coupling light into single-mode fibres is achieving high coupling efficiency. The coupling efficiency can be calculated using Equation (4) [24, 25]:

$$\mu = \frac{|\int E_0 E_1^* dA|^2}{\int |E_0|^2 dA \int |E_1|^2 dA} \quad (4)$$

where E_0 corresponds to the incoming electric field from the telescope and E_1 to the electric field distribution of an optical fibre, which is quite close to a Gaussian function.

In the focal plane, the point spread function (PSF) of a star is approximately a Gaussian distribution, which will lead to a high coupling efficiency in the core of the PSF. Coupling efficiency decreases in the wings of the Airy disk, with the single-mode fibre effectively acting as a spatial filter. In this particular application, however, we are interested in coupling the pupil plane, which has a lower coupling efficiency. In the presence of atmospheric turbulence, the coupling efficiency decays faster with seeing.

The introduction of an array of microlenses in the pupil plane to slice the wavefront will increase the coupling efficiency, as smaller wavefront subapertures experience reduced aberrations. This effect is analogous to reducing the telescope aperture size, since atmospheric turbulence has a stronger impact on larger apertures. The pupil image at the entrance of an array of optical fibres is depicted in Figure 5 for arrays of 2x2, 4x4 and 8x8 fibres. As the microlens size decreases, the wavefront coupled into each individual fibre becomes more spatially homogeneous, thereby improving the coupling efficiency of each channel.

Figure 5: Wavefront images at the input of fibre arrays with 2x2, 4x4 and 8x8 configurations.

In [26], a method was presented that eliminates the need for optical fibres to couple light between the telescope and the Photonic Integrated Circuit (PIC). In this approach, a photonic phase corrector for adaptive optics systems is introduced, in which an image of the telescope pupil is generated on a microlens array. The microlens array then concentrates the light onto a grating coupler, see Figure 6. Using platforms with commercially available grating couplers, an end-to-end simulation reported a coupling efficiency of approximately 30%. However, the authors mentioned that with optimised strategies and a dedicated design, the efficiency could be increased to nearly 80%.

Although grating couplers have not yet been demonstrated on any InP platform, their potential is noteworthy. This coupling method could be especially beneficial if future versions of the WFS are to be implemented on platforms such as SOI or Si₃N₄. This could be a promising implementation that could be applied to this design in the future.

4. RESULTS

Simulations of the performance of the proposed wavefront sensor and corrector were carried out using the open-source, Python-based adaptive optics simulation packages OOPAO [27] and AOTOOLS [28]. The system was evaluated for microlens arrays of 2x2, 4x4, 8x8, and 10x10 subapertures, as well as for the case without adaptive optics correction. Seeing conditions ranging from 0.001 arcsec (diffraction-limited) to 1.1 arcsec were

Figure 6: PIC coupling using the method described in [26]. A microlens array is placed in the pupil, and each portion of the wavefront is coupled to the PIC waveguides using grating couplers.

considered for an 8-m-class telescope. This telescope size has been chosen because is an intermediate size between night-time telescopes, whose current size range up to the 10.4-m Gran Telescopio de Canarias (GTC), and solar telescopes, which range up to the 4-m Daniel K. Inouye Solar Telescope (DKIST) or the future European Solar Telescope (EST), being a worst-case simulation for the last one.

The simulations has been performed using a sensing wavelength of $1.55 \mu m$, a common wavelength for a lot of integrated photonic platforms. In Figure 7 the results performing wavefront correction at a central wavelength of $\lambda_c = 1.55 \mu m$ (J-band), the same as the sensing wavelength, are presented.

(a) Strehl Ratio vs. seeing for a target in the J-band at $\lambda_c = 1.55 \mu m$.

(b) Percentual improvement of the Strehl Ratio vs. seeing for a target in the J-band at $\lambda_c = 1.55 \mu m$.

Figure 7: Strehl Ratio vs. seeing for an 8-m telescope.

It can be observed that the SR ratio improves when an array of microlenses is introduced for both wavelengths. For realistic seeing conditions of 0.5 arcsec, the SR improves from 0.672 to 0.906, representing an improvement of 23.39% in the K-band. A maximum improvement of the Strehl ratio of 25.35% is observed at a seeing value of 0.7 arcsec. It can be observed that for large seeing values, the correction with a low density of microlens worsens the results in comparison with the open loop.

The analysis has also been performed for different photometric bands at different wavelengths, at a seeing value of 0.7 arcsec. The results are shown in Figure 8. The results show how, as expected, for wavelengths below the sensing wavelength of 1550 nm, the AO system has a poor response. This is due to the fact that for shorter wavelengths there is an under-sampling of the wavefront. A peak in SR improvement is achieved between 1550 nm and 1654 nm, with a maximum improvement of 25.4% for a microlens array of 10x10.

(a) Strehl Ratio vs. wavelength for different microlens arrays.

(b) Strehl Ratio improvement when the AO loop is closed for different wavelengths.

Figure 8: Strehl Ratio vs. wavelength for an 8-m telescope at a seeing of 0.7 arcsec.

5. PHYSICAL IMPLEMENTATION

A first prototype implementation of a 2 pixel demonstrator wavefront sensing and correction has been done using a commercial Indium Phosphide (InP) technology; see Figure 9. The chip is $2 \times 8 \text{ mm}^2$ in size and comprises a total of 2 inputs, 2 outputs, and 2 assembly monitoring inputs. There are a total of 22 electrical connections, taking into account both photodiode outputs and component control signals.

This photonic chip operates at a central wavelength of 1550 nm, common for most integrated photonic foundries. It directly applies the schematic in Figure 3. Fabrication is planned through a multi-project wafer (MPW) run, which shares fabrication costs among several projects and enables low-cost implementation of such devices.

InP has been selected as the platform for this first prototype because it allows the possibility of integrating active photonic components, such as photodetectors, and passive components on the same chip. This allows for the replacement of wavefront cameras with photodetectors, reducing the cost of the AO system. Another positive point of this platform is the fact that there are several foundries.

In the future, this design could be implemented in other platforms, such as SOI or Si_3N_4 , that offer the integration of components such as grating couplers, which are not available in commercial InP foundries. In addition, these platforms have the advantage that their components have low losses, which is crucial for astronomical applications.

Figure 9: Layout implementation of a 2 pixels demonstrator wavefront corrector.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Astrophotonics is a novel field with promising features that could lead to the development of new astronomical instruments, as well as to improving the existing ones. The use of integrated photonics in astrophysics instrumen-

tation is experiencing rapid growth, driven by substantial investment and research efforts from both academic institutions and industry, aimed at advancing current photonic technologies.

In this paper, a novel application of integrated photonics for wavefront sensing and correction is proposed. The main advantage of this implementation is that the wavefront camera and the deformable mirror are substituted by photonic components, which could be integrated on-chip. Furthermore, the fact that there is no need for imaging to perform wavefront sensing represents an advantage compared with Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensors.

A chip designed to operate at a wavelength of 1550 nm has been designed for phase detection through interferometry. This chip is planned to be fabricated on a multi-project wafer (MPW) run using commercial InP technology. This enables cost-effective fabrication and rapid prototyping. This design could be adapted to any other platform, such as SOI or Si_3N_4 .

Simulations were performed using open-source Python-based adaptive optics packages, demonstrating an improvement in the Strehl ratio achieved with the proposed wavefront sensing methodology. In addition, the Strehl ratio was evaluated across different photometric bands.

As this technology continues to mature, integration of Complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) technology on chip could enable the realisation of fully integrated photonic instruments. This is of special interest, because currently the number of electrical connections grows exponentially with the number of pixels present in the WFS. Integrating on-chip electronics therefore represents a promising approach to reducing system complexity and interconnection requirements.

Future work will focus on experimental fabrication of this photonic chip, followed by laboratory testing using laser for the experimental validation of this design. Then, a research on potential commercial foundries that allows a higher integration of pixels will be done, in order to achieve a sufficient number of sensing elements for closed-loop validation under controlled wavefront aberrations.

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